

A Novel Driver Performance Model Based on Machine Learning

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Abstract: Models of road vehicle driver behaviour are widely used in several disciplines, like driver distraction and autonomous driving. In this paper, a novel driver performance model, which is unique for every driver, is introduced. The driver is modelled with machine learning algorithms, namely artificial neural network and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system. Every model is trained and validated with the data collected during the real-time driver-in-the-loop experiment on a vehicle simulator for each driver separately. In total, 18 participants contributed to the experiment. Although the prediction accuracy of the models depends on the algorithm specifications, the artificial neural network was slightly more accurate in driver performance prediction comparing to the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system. The driver models may be used in detection of driver distraction induced by in-vehicle information system.

Keywords: Neural networks; Neural fuzzy modelling and control; Machine learning for environmental applications; Vehicle dynamic systems; Human factors in vehicular system; Learning and adaptation in autonomous vehicles; Safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2016, 25500 people died and 135000 were seriously injured in traffic accidents in Europe alone (European Commission, 2017). Thanks to the traffic policies (e.g. obligatory seat belt usage) and in-vehicle active and passive safety features, such as anti-lock braking system, electronic stability program, lane departure warning, and many others, road fatality rates have dramatically decreased within past 10 years (European Commission, 2016). Nevertheless, the traffic safety is still a very serious environmental challenge we are involved in today.

Every year, almost half of the lost lives in road accidents are due to improper driver behaviour. The most dangerous driver mistakes are speeding, driving under the alcohol or forbidden drugs influence, and driver distraction. Traffic safety foundations (e.g. the European Commission Directorate General for Mobility & Transport and the AAA Foundation for Traffic Safety) along with vehicle manufacturers are constantly working on new ideas dedicated to road safety improvement. The first ones mainly focus on transport policies establishment and road environment improvement. The seconds concentrate on advanced driver assistance systems development to reduce driver workload and to avoid driver's inattention, and induced by in-vehicle information system driver distraction diminishment.

Driver modelling is successfully used in development of autonomous driving systems. For instance, lane change (Vallon et al., 2017), trajectory forecasting (Doshi and

Trivedi, 2011), and human-like steering or lane keeping control model (Hubschneider et al., 2017; Kolekar et al., 2017; Saleh et al., 2011) were introduced previously. In addition, Pasquier et al. (2001) developed an automated driver prototype model, which emulates human driving expertise with self-organising fuzzy rule-base system.

Another widely used discipline, where driver modelling is useful, is driver distraction with secondary activity. Driver distraction is defined as "anything that delays the recognition of information necessary to safely maintain the lateral and longitudinal control of the vehicle (driver's primary task) due to some event, activity, object or person, within or outside the vehicle that compels or tends to induce the driver's shifting attention away from the fundamental driving task by compromising the driver's auditory, biomechanical, cognitive or visual faculties or combinations thereof" (Hansen et al., 2017). Driver's secondary tasks are defined as all the activities different from primary tasks the drivers perform while driving.

Brookhuis et al. (1991) made a comparison between normal driving and driving with cell phone interaction. These scholars studied heartrate indices and some of vehicle performance measures. Wang et al. (2015) presented a driver distraction start and end period prediction based on brain activity measured by electroencephalographic signals. The signals were monitored online with an adaptive-threshold-based prediction framework. Choudhary and Velaga (2017) collected driver performance data under a non-distracted driving. Thereafter, non-distracted driver performance was

compared to the driving with mobile phone use applying an analysis of variance test. Simple comparison is not enough for accurate driver distraction study. Therefore, driver modelling is necessary to conduct the research on different distraction case studies.

Hermannstädter and Yang (2013) applied a driver model adopted from literature to real-road driving of a distracted experiment in order to assess the driver state. The distraction experiment data comprised real road driving with distraction, as well as reference driving. The driver model features an anticipatory and a compensatory tracking component, a processing time delay, and a neuromuscular subsystem with a torque control loop. Yang et al. (2010) developed a two-class classifier based on driver behavior for driver distraction using the nonlinear extended two-wheel vehicle dynamic model. However, in both references, the models are derived mathematically and have many approximations comparing to the real driving performance.

Ersal et al. (2010) proposed a model-based approach to analyse different effects of secondary tasks on individual driver. For this, the authors introduced a radial-basis model-network-based modelling framework for normal (not distracted) driving behaviour characterization. Next, the method was combined with support vector machines for normal or distracted driving classification. The driver model was expressed mathematically and was fitted with normal driving data. Unfortunately, the model was used for all drivers and, therefore, was not applicable for individual driver distraction studies.

Kirscher and Ahlstrom (2010) attempted to predict visual distraction with driver performance model. Based on the results, each experiment participant was classified as either distracted or attentive. Five-class drowsy driving classifier was introduced in (Matsuo and Khiat, 2012). The authors monitored driver's behaviour (i.e. head sway, eye closure rate, and frequency of subsidiary behaviour).

This work is dedicated to driver model development, which is capable to predict each individual driver normal driving on a specific road segment with a reasonable degree of accuracy. Thus, machine learning techniques, like classification, proposed by other researchers (Kirscher and Ahlstrom, 2010; Matsuo and Khiat, 2012; Ersal et al., (2010)) are not suitable for accurate driver modelling, because driver performance is a highly nonlinear activity and cannot be limited with several classes (Alpaydin, 2004). Contrariwise, nonlinear regression methods, where the predicted responses are real numbers, are efficient in accurate prediction from data sample. Hence, machine learning algorithms, namely artificial neural network (ANN) and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), are applied in this paper for driver performance modelling.

Moreover, the model depends on each driver individual performance and unique for every driver. The model does not require complex mathematical representation, like the ones proposed in (Hermannstädter and Yang, 2013; Yang et al., 2010; Ersal et al., 2010).

To verify driver models, driver performance data were collected for each individual participant in driver-in-the-loop experiment using a vehicle simulator. Next, the unique performance models for every driver were built. Finally, new data were obtained on the same testbed to test the prediction accuracy for each participant separately.

The models refer to the road segments, which are defined by road curvature and speed limit. Thus, the models predict driver's manoeuvrability on a specific road section. The predicted variables are road middle line keeping and speed limit maintenance abilities for each individual participant.

In next section, the driver models are designed. Data collection and driver-in-the-loop experiment is described in Section 3. In Section 4, the experimental results of driver performance prediction are introduced and are discussed. Finally, the research is concluded in Section 5.

2. DRIVER MODELS

In Fig. 1, a driver model is presented. It receives an information about a road as the inputs, which characterize a road segment: curvature (radius) r and speed limit V_l . The information about the road is instantaneous. Two variables describe driver performance. The first one is a difference between a vehicle velocity and a road segment speed limitation (speed error) Δv . The second output is a distance between a road middle line and vehicle geometric centreline (line error) Δx . For simplicity, both variables are accepted as absolute values. Therefore, a driver model forecasts, how well a person drives in the middle of the lane and maintains the speed limit on various road segments.

Drivers are modelled with machine learning algorithms. In this paper, two methods, namely ANN and ANFIS, are applied independently. Both the ANN and the ANFIS are trained and tested with the data set gathered separately for every experiment participant. In this regard, the participants drive a vehicle simulator for three laps, two of which are exploited in algorithms training, and the third one – for prediction precision testing. The results of the algorithms prediction accuracies are compared for both algorithms.

Both the ANN and the ANFIS are the reasoning models based on human brain. They are widely used as nonlinear regression algorithms. In fact, ANFIS is a symbiosis of an ANN and fuzzy logic. For both algorithms training the sample data are required. Here, the same data are exploited for both models' training.

Driver models are designed in MATLAB® R2016b from

Fig. 1. Driver performance model.

MathWorks, Inc. (Natick, Massachusetts, USA) environment. The Fuzzy Logic Toolbox™ was exploited for ANFIS, and the Neural Network Toolbox™ was applied in ANN modelling. The ANN and the ANFIS practical designing guidance can be found in (Negnevitsky, 2005).

2.1 Artificial Neural Network

The feedforward ANN constructed in this work has an input layer, hidden layer with 500 neurons, and output layer. For maximum performance accuracy, it is recommended to use as much neurons in hidden layers as possible, if it does not bring a network overfitting. The number of neurons were selected with trial and error method. In this respect, several ANNs with 100 to 1000 neurons were designed and were compared between each other. Better network performance was not discerned with more than 500 neurons.

Initially, the hyperparameters are set by default in the Toolbox, while the training parameters (i.e. initial weights and threshold levels) are selected randomly. The last ones are uniformly distributed inside a small range, whose limits depend on a number of inputs of a neuron in the network.

Hyperbolic tangent transfer functions are applied to hidden layers, because of their simplicity and good performance. The output neuron transfer functions are linear. The ANN is trained with Levenberg-Marquardt learning algorithm, because it is the most popular, fast, and widely used approach in nonlinear regression. In this algorithm, a backward propagation of errors (back-propagation) method is applied for gradients computation. It employs a dynamic programming strategy to reuse rather than re-compute partial sums associated with the gradients on intermediate nodes, what makes the back-propagation approach one of the fastest and the most efficient methods (Goodfellow et al., 2016).

2.2 Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System

An ANFIS performance mainly depends on the membership functions (MFs) quantity, and less – on the MFs type. Nevertheless, the MFs' shape is mostly responsible for the output smoothness and reaction time. A number of MFs is

proportional to a number of linguistic rules. Higher number of fuzzy rules allows more precise network tuning.

Like ANN, the ANFIS model is designed with trial and error method. In particular, different MF numbers and shapes were studied. The significantly better model performance was achieved with nine Gaussian shape MFs for each input. The MFs are symmetrically dispersed and overlap between each other over the whole universe of discourse.

In total, 81 rules were generated after training the ANFIS. As ANFIS is an equivalent to a first-order Sugeno fuzzy model, the output MFs are 81 singletons, which were tuned automatically. Defuzzification method is a weighted average. Hybrid training method composed of the least-squares estimator and the gradient descent methods was applied.

3. DATA COLLECTION

3.1 Participants

Overall, 13 male and 5 female participated in a driver-in-the-loop experiment. The participation in the experiment was voluntary and did not intend a reward. The drivers were workers of the IPG Automotive GmbH (Karlsruhe, Germany). Every one owned a valid driver license and had at least one year of driving experience in Europe.

The youngest driver was 24 years old, and the oldest – 39. Average participants' age was 30.1 years old. The most experienced driver owned a driving license for 21 years, while the average driving experience was 11.3 years.

3.2 Apparatus

In Fig. 2, the experiment facilities are shown. The driver simulator System Experience Platform was provided by the IPG Automotive GmbH (Karlsruhe, Germany). The vehicle mockup includes an automatic gearbox, a steering wheel, pedals (i.e. gas and brake), and an adjustable driver's seat. The virtual world is depicted on a liquid-crystal screen in front of the driver, where the vehicle speed, road shape, and vehicle position on the route were displayed.

Fig. 2. Driver-in-the-loop experiment simulator.

Fig. 3. Road shape and segments speed limitations.

The test-rig runs a vehicle model from IPG CarMaker® (Karlsruhe, Germany). It is capable for real-time integration with MATLAB® (Natick, Massachusetts, USA) environment. Thus, it allows conducting real-time drive-in-the-loop experiments. The data are saved with 50 Hz frequency.

A two-lane rural highway road with different curvatures and speed limits (i.e. 30, 50, and 90 km/h) was modelled in the virtual world. Its distance was 10 626 m/lap. The road shape along with the speed limitations is introduced in Fig. 3. One lap requires about ten minutes of driving, when all the traffic rules are obeyed. There were no other dynamic objects (e.g. pedestrians, other vehicles) introduced in the virtual world. However, many different static objects (e.g. trees, houses, traffic signs) were designed in the simulated world.

3.3 Procedure

The experiment participants' mission was to drive the simulator respecting all the traffic rules, reading and following all the traffic signs. In particular, their main task was to drive in the middle of the lane and to maintain the speed limits as precisely as manageable. Not to mention that all the drivers had an opportunity to pass one lap to become acquainted with the test-rig before the test, due to time

restriction each participant drove only three full laps during the experiment.

The data collected during the first two laps were utilized for each individual driver performance modelling. Every driver passes the same road segment in different way. Although the difference is very small, every driver completes the same road segment slightly differently. By this reason, the data gathered from driving at least two identical laps is necessary. The data from the third lap were utilized in the ANN and the ANFIS prediction performance testing.

4. RESULTS

The results of the driver performance prediction for a random driver are presented in this section. For different driver-in-the-loop experiment participants the results of the models prediction accuracy are very similar. From three laps driving around 80 000 nodes were collected for each individual driver. These data were divided into a training data (67%) and a testing (33%) for every participant separately. Therefore, the data from approximately two full laps were applied to driver performance model design, whereas the data from the last lap were exploited for models testing. The models were trained and verified off-line, after the driver-in-

Fig. 4. Results of the driver performance prediction: red line – testing performance; black line – prediction with ANN; blue line – prediction with ANFIS; green line – information about the road segment.

the-loop experiment. The procedures are unique for every participant. Therefore, every performance model is suitable for a single driver only.

In Fig. 4, the prediction results along with models test are presented. The red curve symbolizes the test data gathered from the last lap. The black line is a predicted result by the ANN, while the blue line – by the ANFIS. Both the ANN and the ANFIS have very similar driver modelling results. For most of the experiment period, performance results by the ANN overlap with the performance results by the ANFIS.

In Fig. 4, the green curve represents an information about the road segment, namely road speed limitation and curvature. The prediction models read an instantaneous information about the road shape and speed limitation. The lap can be roughly divided into two parts (Fig. 3). The first part has a lower speed limitation (i.e. 30 and 50 km/h) and frequent curvature. The participant drove this part for the first 250 seconds (Fig. 4). The second part has a higher speed limit of 90 km/h with a high road radius, which the driver passed for the rest of the validation time (Fig. 4).

In Fig. 4, upper scope, the speed limit maintenance ability Δv is introduced. Both the ANN and the ANFIS predict slight oscillation in ability to keep speed limit for the first road part. Roughly, the predicted Δv varies between 2 and 4 km/h. In fact, the driver did not hold the speed limit precisely. The error oscillates between 0 and 6 km/h without noticeable extremums. Thus, the prediction is reasonable enough considering that the road on this segment is very curvy.

On the second road phase with higher speed limit (i.e. 90 km/h), the models show a high error in speed maintenance, when the limits were changed from 30 km/h to 90 km/h. An average driver is not able to instantly accelerate the vehicle or drop the speed to its road speed limit. Consequently, this phenomena is detected by the model.

Moreover, on the speedy segment there are also two curvy phases (Fig. 3). Both the ANN and the ANFIS recognize a significant speed reduction, and the driver dropped the speed on this segment during the last validation lap as well (Fig. 4 inset, upper scope). The rest of the segment the predicted vehicle velocity was almost linear, around 3 km/h faster or slower than its road limit. The driver, however, passed the rest of the road with smaller speed limit maintenance error, what was unusual for her/his algorithms training phase.

In Fig. 4, lower scope, a middle line keeping ability Δx is shown. The first part of the road is characterized with frequent curvature (Fig. 3; Fig. 4, green curve). It is obvious that lane keeping ability is harder. The amplitude is predicted by the machine learning algorithms, where in average the participant drove further than 0.5 m away from the middle of the lane. The red curve on the plot indeed proves the same driver's behaviour on the road segment with frequent vehicle body lateral oscillation. In some moment during the third validation lap, the participant passed the segment with considerably high error.

On the second road part, the ANN and the ANFIS demonstrate almost linear behaviour, where the driver was

Table 1. Algorithms comparison

Algorithm	$e_{\Delta v}$	$e_{\Delta x}$	Training time [s]
ANN	2.7243	0.2712	379
ANFIS	2.8294	0.2742	549

able to stay in the middle of the road with slightly less than 0.5 m error to the left or to the right during the training period. Nevertheless, during the validation the vehicle body also oscillates on this segment, but with longer period.

Thus, the networks approximate the driver performance almost linearly. It is worth to point out that on the two curvy segments on the speedy curve the driver was able to keep the road lane with the same error as predicted by the networks (Fig. 4 inset, lower scope). It can be concluded that this driver tends to drop the speed limit on this specific road shape rather than cut the road curve (Fig. 4, insets), this characterizes the specific behaviour of the particular driver.

The ANN and the ANFIS are compared on prediction accuracy. In this regard, an average error between predicted speed limit maintenance and real vehicle speed $e_{\Delta v}$ and an average error between predicted and real middle line keeping ability $e_{\Delta x}$ are calculated. The results are presented in Table 1. Although it was not important in our studies, the algorithms training times are delivered in Table 1. In short, the designed ANN driver model conducted more accurate prediction than the ANFIS model. However, in this experiment, the difference in prediction is insignificant.

The prediction by the ANFIS is also somewhat smoother than by the ANN. It can be explained by the ANFIS algorithm itself, because it uses a fuzzy set theory applying the training capabilities for the rule-base optimization. Although, it depends on the fuzzy logic MFs, mostly the algorithm is more smooth and precise in control or decision making systems (Negnevitsky, 2005). In fact, a smooth MFs types (Gaussian shape) were used in this paper.

Networks predict driver performance with almost 3 km/h and 0.3 m error for Δv and Δx , respectively. Considering that Δv ([0 50]) has higher amplitude than Δx ([0 2]), the driver models are accepted as reasonably accurate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the driver models with machine learning algorithms are introduced. Two nonlinear regression methods, namely ANN and ANFIS, were independently designed to predict driver's middle lane and speed limit keeping abilities. The models are based on the road segments characterized by curvature and speed limitation.

The ANN and the ANFIS were developed with the sample data, collected on a vehicle simulator during a ride in a virtual world. Eighteen drivers participated in the driver-in-the-loop experiment. Thereafter, each driver passed one additional lap, which was used for algorithms accuracy testing of each individual participant. Although the ANN prediction was more accurate comparing to the ANFIS, the

difference in prediction is negligibly small. Overall, both the ANN and the ANFIS prediction accuracy are satisfactory.

The ANN and the ANFIS models have the significant benefits over proposed previously driver performance models for driver distraction studies, where the classification algorithms incapable for accurate driver distraction investigation were introduced. Proposed in this work driver models allow more accurate driver performance analysis. In the future, these models will be combined with driver distraction evaluation method (Aksjonov et. al., 2017) to develop a practical tool for in-vehicle information system human-machine interaction technologies assessment.

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